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The effect of e-commerce, the use of accounting information systems and financial knowledge in decision making for entrepreneurship

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Abstract

An entrepreneur is said to be able to compete in the business world when they are able to adapt to the changes that occur, including technological developments. The development of information technology in today's business world plays an important role for entrepreneurs in running and developing their businesses. This is because information technology provides convenience for transactions in an efficient and effective manner. The existence of information technology today has led to an increase in entrepreneurs utilizing and using information technology. This study aims to obtain evidence regarding the effect of e-commerce, the use of accounting information systems, and financial knowledge on decision-making for entrepreneurship. This research was conducted at Warmadewa University. The data collection method used in this study was a survey method with a questionnaire technique. The population in this study were accounting students at Bachelor Degree, Diploma Degree, and Associate Degree levels at Warmadewa University who have status as active students. The data used in this study is primary data obtained by distributing questionnaires directly to respondents using a purposive sampling technique. The data analysis used is multiple linear regression.

Keywords: E-Commerce; Use of Accounting Information Systems; Financial Knowledge; Entrepreneurs

1. Introduction

The business world in Indonesia currently has a global market or level of competition that is still relatively low. The requirement for a country to achieve a level of prosperity requires that 2% of the total population be entrepreneurs (Margareta & Erma Setiawati, 2019). According to the Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs, the number of Indonesian entrepreneurs in 2021 will be 3.74%, while Malaysia, Singapore, and Thailand will be above 4%. The number of entrepreneurs in Thailand is 4.2%, Malaysia is 4.7%, and Singapore is 8.7%. When compared to neighboring countries, it must be admitted that entrepreneurs in Indonesia are still relatively small.

Entrepreneurship is the process of identifying, developing, and bringing vision and creativity to make it happen so that it can affect the surrounding environment. The phenomenon of entrepreneurship among young people today is becoming increasingly popular. Entrepreneurship is currently a hope for the economies of developing nations, including Indonesia (Putra & Astri, 2015). E-Commerce is a business mechanism that is carried out electronically, focusing on technology-based business processes, by using the internet network as an exchange of goods and/or services through space and time constraints (Romney & Steinbart, 2018). An accounting information system is a collection of resources, both human and equipment, that provide financial information and information collected from an organization that is designed in such a way as a basis for decision-making (Pramiswari & Dharmadiaksa, 2017). Another factor that can influence interest in entrepreneurship is financial knowledge. Financial knowledge is someone's mastery of something related to finance (Kholilah, 2013).

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Pramiswari & Dharmadiaksa (2017) state that E-Commerce and accounting information systems have a positive effect on decision-making for entrepreneurship. Some of the research results above show that the development of E-Commerce and the existence of accounting information systems can influence the interest of the younger generation, especially students, in entrepreneurship. In contrast to the results of research conducted by Hariadi (2013), where there is no effect between the usefulness of e-commerce and the intentions of e-commerce users in entrepreneurship, research conducted by Sihombing (2021) states that e-commerce and accounting information systems can influence decision-making. Entrepreneurial decisions for Bachelor Degree Accounting students 2016, Singaperbangsa University, Karawang The results of research conducted by Lovita (2021) also found that an understanding of E-Commerce and an understanding of SIA (Accounting Information Systems) have a positive effect on interest in entrepreneurship. For students, understanding E-Commerce and SIA will encourage greater opportunities to successfully run their businesses. The results of previous studies showed inconsistent results. The difference between this research and previous studies is that there is a financial knowledge variable that has never been associated with decision-making variables in entrepreneurship. So based on this background, research was carried out on "The Effect of E-Commerce, Use of Accounting Information Systems, and Financial Knowledge on Decision Making for Entrepreneurship (Study on Undergraduate, Diploma Degree, and Associate Degree Accounting Students at Warmadewa University)". The research was conducted at Warmadewa University because Warmadewa University is one of the private universities that has the most accounting study programs in Bali, namely the Associate Degree Accounting Information Systems Study Program, the Diploma Degree Tax Accounting Study Program, and the Bachelor of Accounting, as a representation of accounting students in Bali.

2. Literature and hypothesis

2.1. Contingency Theory

Contingency theory is a theory that studies how contingent factors such as technology, culture, and the external environment can affect organizational behavior, design, and function (Lubis, 2017). The basic assumption that can be used in contingency theory is that no type of organizational structure is the same, and this assumption applies to various types of organizations. The contingency framework can be a holistic approach to designing a management accounting system.

2.2. E-Commerce

According to Senn (2000), the e-commerce business is very prospective because it can connect sellers and buyers without knowing distance and time limitations through the internet network. This technology began with the discovery of ATM cards in 1965, where consumers could withdraw money from Automated Teller Machines (ATMs) and make transactions using credit cards. E-commerce is the buying and selling of goods and services using the internet. On the consumer side, the internet is often used as a source of information for comparing prices or simply viewing the latest products offered before making purchasing decisions online or offline. On the producer side, the use of the internet has also changed the way a company runs its business, namely the way it deals with customers and suppliers, as well as in terms of marketing and logistics (Lindsay, 2002).

2.3. Accounting Information System (SIA)

According to Bodnar & Hapwood (2006), SIA is a computer-based system created so that accounting data can become more useful information, which includes transaction flow processes, the application of information technology, and being able to keep up with the times. Puspawati & Anggadini (2014) state in their book that SIA is a system that is useful in creating and providing forms, records, and reports that are important in obtaining financial information needed to make management decisions and company leaders decisions quickly, thereby making it easier to manage the company. SIA consists of elements that cannot be separated, and each of these elements will complement each other so as to produce an accurate report.

2.4. Financial Knowledge

According to Kholilah and Iramani (2013), financial knowledge is a person's mastery of various matters regarding the financial world. Financial knowledge is an integral dimension of financial literacy. Financial literacy has a dimension that implies a person must have the ability and confidence to use financial knowledge in making financial decisions. In other words, financial knowledge is a conceptual definition of financial literacy (Huston, 2010).

Financial knowledge consists of four things, as mentioned by Chen & Volpe (1998), namely:

- General Knowledge of Finance

General knowledge of finance is knowledge of a person's ability to manage personal financial assets.\

- Knowledge of Savings and Loans

Knowledge of savings is one's knowledge of managing money savings, or a number of funds that are not used at a certain time.

- Insurance Knowledge

Insurance knowledge is knowledge about financial protection in order to get reimbursement from unexpected events (risks that may arise) through the payment of an amount of funds to the risk bearer.

- Investment Knowledge

Investment knowledge is knowledge about an act of releasing funds now with the aim of obtaining a flow of funds in the future by obtaining a larger amount of funds.

2.5. Entrepreneurship

According to Suryana & Bayu (2011), an entrepreneur is someone who is creative in creating new businesses with the courage to accept losses and uncertainties and who aims to gain profits and develop their business by identifying potential and being able to utilize resources and accommodate this potential. Entrepreneurship consists of two important elements, namely: (1) opportunities and (2) the ability to respond to these opportunities. Thus, entrepreneurship can be interpreted as the spirit, behavior, and ability to respond positively to existing opportunities, which aims to gain personal benefits or create better service to customers by improving service, creating more useful products, improving work efficiency, having the courage to take risks, being creative, and being innovative, as well as having managerial ability.

2.6. Research Hypothesis

2.6.1. *Effect of E-Commerce on Decision Making for Entrepreneurship*

E-Commerce (Electronic Commerce) is a business mechanism that is carried out electronically, focusing on technology-based business processes, by using the internet network as an exchange of goods and/or services through space and time constraints (Romney & Steinbart, 2018). E-commerce is a system that can be run if there is an internet network and can function as a platform for the process of buying, selling, marketing goods and services, and processing payments (Sutanto, 2000).

According to Lubis (2017), contingency theory is an approach that studies how contingent factors such as technology, culture, and the external environment can affect organizational behavior, design, and function. One of the factors that influence a person's decision-making in entrepreneurship is E-Commerce, where the system is already digital-based and entrepreneurs can market their products without face-to-face meetings with customers, which will facilitate business activities and make people interested in entrepreneurship.

Research conducted by Pramiswari and Dharmadiaksa (2017) states that e-commerce has a positive effect on entrepreneurial decision-making. Research conducted by Sihombing (2021) states that e-commerce can influence entrepreneurial decision-making for 2016 Bachelor of Accounting students at Singaperbangsa University, Karawang. The results of the study show that the development of e-commerce can influence the interest of the younger generation, especially students, in entrepreneurship. The higher the use of e-commerce, the higher a person's decision-making for entrepreneurship, so the hypothesis is:

H₁: E-Commerce has a positive effect on decision-making for entrepreneurship Bachelor Degree, Diploma Degree and Associate Degree Accounting students at Warmadewa University.

2.6.2. *The Effect of Using Accounting Information Systems on Decision Making for Entrepreneurship*

An accounting information system is a collection of resources, both human and equipment, that provide financial information and information collected from an organization that is designed in such a way as a basis for decision-making

(Pramiswari & Dharmadiaksa, 2017). Accounting information systems are useful for financial management (Wulandari et al., 2020). Accounting information systems can also increase efficiency and effectiveness in decision-making so as to enable companies to obtain the desired benefits (Yadewani & Wijaya, 2017).

Contingency theory is an approach that studies how contingent factors such as technology, culture, and the external environment can influence organizational behavior, design, and function (Lubis, 2017). One of the factors that influence a person's decision-making in entrepreneurship is the use of an accounting information system. This system can increase efficiency and effectiveness, which will facilitate business activities, so that people will be interested in entrepreneurship.

Research conducted by Pramiswari and Dharmadiaksa (2017) states that the use of accounting information systems has a positive effect on decision-making in entrepreneurship. Research conducted by Sihombing (2021) states that the use of accounting information systems can influence entrepreneurial decision-making for 2016 Bachelor of Accounting students at Singaperbangsa University, Karawang. The results of the study show that the development of accounting information systems can influence the interest of the younger generation, especially students, in entrepreneurship. The higher the use of accounting information systems, the higher a person's decision-making for entrepreneurship, so the hypothesis is:

H₂: The use of Accounting Information Systems has a positive effect on decision-making for entrepreneurship Bachelor Degree, Diploma Degree, and Associate Degree Accounting students at Warmadewa University.

2.6.3. Effect of Financial Knowledge on Decision Making for Entrepreneurship

Financial knowledge is someone's mastery of something related to finance (Kholilah, 2013). Various sources of knowledge can be obtained through formal and informal education. Financial knowledge has the goal of allowing an individual to have the ability and confidence in financial matters so that they can make decisions related to finance (Huston, 2010). Financial knowledge is needed to deal with financial problems systematically.

Contingency theory is an approach that studies how contingent factors such as technology, culture, and the external environment can influence organizational behavior, design, and function (Lubis, 2017). One of the factors that effects one's decision-making in entrepreneurship is financial knowledge. Someone who has an interest in entrepreneurship must understand how to manage company finances in order to generate the desired profit. Entrepreneurs who have financial knowledge will be able to prepare and know what the financial condition of their business is. Mature knowledge from the financial side will attract someone to make a decision to become an entrepreneur because it can predict the finances of his business so that the profit generated will be in accordance with the desired target, so the hypothesis is:

H₃: Financial knowledge has a positive effect on decision-making for entrepreneurship undergraduates and Diploma Degree and Associate Degree Accounting students at Warmadewa University.

3. Material and method

Table 1 Sample Selection Process

No.	Criteria	Number of Companies
1.	Associate Degree, Diploma Degree and Bachelor Degree Accounting students at Warmadewa University.	1.554
2.	Unreturned questionnaires.	(417)
3.	Associate Degree, Diploma Degree, and Bachelor Degree Accounting students at Warmadewa University who have not taken the Accounting Information Systems course.	(431)
4.	Warmadewa University Associate Degree, Diploma Degree, and Bachelor Degree Accounting students who have not taken the Entrepreneurship course.	(413)
5.	Students who do not have the desire to become entrepreneurs.	(58)
Number of Student Samples		235

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

Respondents in this study were all Associate Degree, Diploma Degree, and Bachelor Degree accounting students at Warmadewa University, Denpasar, Bali. This study used a purposive sampling technique, namely the technique of determining the sample with certain considerations. Based on this, the number of respondents in this study was 235. The research questionnaire began to be distributed on May 1, 2023, through June 5, 2023. Data collection was carried out by visiting respondents in person or online to submit and re-collect the questionnaire. Of the 1554 questionnaires distributed by the researchers, 1337 copies were returned, and 902 copies did not meet the criteria. Thus, the number of questionnaires that can be processed is 235 copies (details in Table 1).

The characteristics of the respondents in this study are based on the profiles of the 235 respondents who participated in filling out the questionnaire. Based on the 235 questionnaires that can be processed, the profiles of the respondents are obtained as a reference for viewing the characteristics of the respondents who are the research sample. As for the description of the profile of respondents in this study, namely, level/study program, gender, position, and length of work, the characteristics of the 146 respondents who participated in this study are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Characteristics of Respondents

Explanation	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Study Program		
Bachelor Degree/ Accounting	187	79
Diploma Degree/Tax Accounting	42	18
Associate Degree /SIA	6	3
Total	235	100
Gender		
Male	64	27
Female	171	73
Total	235	100
Semester		
II/ Bachelor Degree	64	27
IV/ Bachelor Degree	92	39
IV/ Diploma Degree	8	3
IV/ Associate Degree	4	2
VI/ Bachelor Degree	30	13
VI/ Diploma Degree	13	6
VI/ Associate Degree	2	0.7
VIII/ Bachelor Degree	1	0.3
VIII/ Diploma Degree	21	9
Total	235	100

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

3.1. Research Instrument Testing Results

3.1.1. Validity Test

The minimum requirement for a questionnaire to fulfill validity is if the coefficient value is above 0.3. The correlation value between item scores and total items is then compared to the critical r (0.30). If the correlation to the total score item is greater than 0.30, the research instrument is said to be valid with a significance level of 0.05 (Sugiyono, 2019). This study used an internal validity test because the instrument adopted a questionnaire from previous research. The

researchers previously conducted validity tests on respondents outside the sample, where before the instrument was given to the sample respondents and it was declared valid. The results of the validity test are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Validity Test Results

No	Variable	Indicator	Correlation coefficient	Significance Value	Explanation
1.	E-Commerce (X1)	X1.1	0,638	0,000	Valid
		X1.2	0,623	0,000	Valid
		X1.3	0,664	0,000	Valid
		X1.4	0,629	0,000	Valid
		X1.5	0,604	0,000	Valid
		X1.6	0,543	0,000	Valid
		X1.7	0,644	0,000	Valid
		X1.8	0,680	0,000	Valid
2.	Use of Accounting Information Systems (X2)	X2.1	0,725	0,000	Valid
		X2.2	0,642	0,000	Valid
		X2.3	0,661	0,000	Valid
		X2.4	0,636	0,000	Valid
		X2.5	0,702	0,000	Valid
		X2.6	0,711	0,000	Valid
3.	Financial Knowledge (X3)	X3.1	0,619	0,000	Valid
		X3.2	0,599	0,000	Valid
		X3.3	0,540	0,000	Valid
		X3.4	0,626	0,000	Valid
		X3.5	0,634	0,000	Valid
		X3.6	0,641	0,000	Valid
4.	Decision Making for Entrepreneurship (Y)	Y1.1	0,667	0,000	Valid
		Y1.2	0,562	0,000	Valid
		Y1.3	0,613	0,000	Valid
		Y1.4	0,666	0,000	Valid
		Y1.5	0,679	0,000	Valid
		Y1.6	0,639	0,000	Valid
		Y1.7	0,639	0,000	Valid

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

Based on the table above, it can be said that the research instrument consisting of e-commerce statement items (X1), use of accounting information systems (X2), financial knowledge (X3), and decision-making for entrepreneurship (Y) is valid. This is due to the correlation between the scores of each statement with a score above 0.30, so that each instrument in this study can be analyzed further.

3.1.2. Reliability Test

The reliability test is used to determine the consistency of the measuring instrument in its use (Sugiyono, 2019). The reliability test with SPSS uses a Statistical Reliability Analysis with a Cronbach's Alpha value greater than 0.60 (Ghozali, 2021). The results of the reliability test are presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4 Reliability Test Results

No	Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Explanation
1	E-Commerce (X1)	0,783	Reliable
2	Use of Accounting Information Systems (X2)	0,767	Reliable
3	Financial Knowledge (X3)	0,674	Reliable
4	Decision Making for Entrepreneurship (Y)	0,768	Reliable

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

The reliability test results shown in Table 4 show that all research instruments are said to be reliable if they are feasible to use to collect data. Cronbach's alpha value > 0.60 indicates that the measurement can provide consistent results if measurements are taken again on the same subject at different times so that each instrument in this study can be analyzed further.

3.1.3. Classical Assumption Test

The classical assumption test aims to find out and test the feasibility of the regression model used in research (Ghozali, 2021). The results of the classical assumption test are shown in Table 5 below.

Table 5 Classical Assumption Test Results

Parameters Tested	Normality Test	Multicollinearity Test		Heteroscedasticity Test
	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	Tolerance	VIF	Sig.
Unstandardized Residual	0,200			
E-Commerce (X1)		0,467	2,139	0,188
Use of Accounting Information Systems (X2)		0,454	2,202	0,065
Financial Knowledge (X3)		0,442	2,263	0,375

Normality test

A good regression model is a normally distributed regression. To test the normality of a data set, look at Asymp. Sig (2-tailed). The criterion used in this test is to compare the significance level obtained with the alpha level used, where the data is said to be normally distributed if Asymp. Sig (2-tailed) $>$ alpha (0.05) (Ghozali, 2021). Based on Table 5, it can be seen that the value of Asymp. Sig (2-tailed) has a value of 0.200, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05. This shows that the equation model is normally distributed, so the research equation model can be tested further.

Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test aims to test whether there is a correlation between the independent variables in the regression model (Ghozali, 2021). So, a low tolerance value is the same as a high VIF value (because $VIF = 1/\text{tolerance}$). The value used to indicate the absence of multicollinearity is a tolerance value ≥ 0.10 or a VIF value ≤ 10 . Based on table 5 it can be seen that the tolerance value of the equation model is above 0.1 and the VIF value is below 10. This shows that the equation model there are no symptoms of multicollinearity, so that the research equation model formed can be tested further.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether the regression model has an unequal variance from the residuals of one observation to another. A good regression model is one that does not contain symptoms of heteroscedasticity. The heteroscedasticity test was carried out using the Glejser test, which regresses the residual absolute value of the estimated model on the independent variables. If the significance level obtained is greater than the alpha level (0.05) used, then it is said that the regression model does not contain heteroscedasticity problems (Ghozali, 2021). Based on Table 5, it is known that the significance value of each variable in the regression model is greater than 0.05, so it can be concluded that the regression model in this study is free from symptoms of heteroscedasticity and the research equation model formed can be tested further.

3.1.4. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistical test results from ordinal data are presented in Table 6 below.

Table 6 Descriptive Statistical Test Results

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Avg	Standard Deviation
E-Commerce (X1)	235	8,00	32,00	27.4638	2.99318
Use of Accounting Information Systems (X2)	235	6,00	24,00	20.3702	2.25963
Financial Knowledge (X3)	235	6,00	24,00	20.5532	2.11636
Decision Making for Entrepreneurship (Y)	235	7,00	28,00	23.8979	2.56167

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

The descriptive statistics table shows the minimum value, maximum value, mean, and standard deviation of each variable.

3.1.5. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test

Table 7 shows the results of multiple linear regression testing with a significance level of 5%.

Table 7 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test Results

Variable	Beta Value	Significance
Statistical Test t		
(Constant)	2.048	0,042
E-Commerce	5.285	0,000
Use of Accounting Information Systems	4.533	0,000
Financial Knowledge	5.896	0,000
Statistical Test F		
Value of F	142.468	
Sig.	0.000	
Determination Coefficient Test		
R Square	0.649	
Adjusted R Square	0.645	
<i>Dependent. Var. Decision to Entrepreneur</i>		

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

Based on Table 7, the regression equation is obtained as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \beta_5X_5 + e \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$Y = 2,048 + 5,285X_1 + 4,533X_2 + 5,896X_3 + e \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

3.1.6. Test the Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

The R^2 test was conducted to measure the model's ability to explain the variation of the independent variables. Table 7 shows the coefficient of determination of 0.649. This means that 64.9% of the variation in the decision to become an entrepreneur can be explained by variations in the three independent variables, namely e-commerce, the use of accounting information systems, and financial knowledge. The remaining 35.1% can be explained by other variables outside of the research.

3.1.7. Model Feasibility Test (F Test)

The F test is called the model feasibility test, which aims to find out if the multiple linear regression model is feasible to use as an analytical tool that examines the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. If the significance in the annova table is less than $\alpha = 0.05$, then the model used is feasible. Based on Table 7, it can be seen that the calculation results from the F test show a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$. This means that the model can be said to be feasible for testing the independent variables on the dependent variable.

3.1.8. Hypothesis Test (t test)

The t test is used to test the hypothesis of the effect of one independent variable on explaining the dependent variable (Ghozali 2021). Table 7 shows that there are three influential variables: e-commerce, the use of accounting information systems, and financial knowledge. This can be seen from the significance probability value for e-commerce of 0.000 ($\rho < 0.05$), the use of accounting information systems of 0.000 ($\rho < 0.05$), and financial knowledge of 0.000 ($\rho < 0.05$). So, it can be concluded that the variables of e-commerce, the use of accounting information systems, and financial knowledge affect the decision variables for entrepreneurship.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Effect of E-Commerce on the Decision to Become an Entrepreneur

The first hypothesis (H_1) states that e-commerce has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur. The results of the analysis in Table 7 show that the positive coefficient value is 5.285 with a significance level of 0.000, which is smaller than the real level in this study, namely $\alpha = 0.05$. This shows that e-commerce has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur. The first hypothesis (H_1) is acceptable, that is, e-commerce has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur, and the greater the effect of e-commerce, the higher the students' decision to pursue entrepreneurship.

Research conducted by Pramiswari and Dharmadiaksa (2017) states that e-commerce has a positive effect on entrepreneurial decision-making. Research conducted by Sihombing (2021) states that e-commerce can influence entrepreneurial decision-making for 2016 Bachelor of Accounting students at Singaperbangsa University, Karawang. The results of the study show that the development of e-commerce can influence the interest of the younger generation, especially students, in entrepreneurship. The higher the use of e-commerce, the higher a person's decision-making for entrepreneurship.

Contingency theory is an approach that studies how contingent factors such as technology, culture, and the external environment can affect organizational behavior, design, and function (Lubis, 2017). One of the factors that influence a person's decision-making in entrepreneurship is e-commerce, where the system is already digital-based and entrepreneurs can market their products without face-to-face meetings with customers, which will facilitate business activities and make people interested in entrepreneurship.

4.2. The Effect of the Use of Accounting Information Systems on Decisions for Entrepreneurship

The second hypothesis (H_2) states that the use of accounting information systems has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur. The results of the analysis in Table 7 show that the positive coefficient value is 4.533 with a significance level of 0.000, which is smaller than the real level in this study, namely $\alpha = 0.05$. This shows that the use of accounting information systems has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur. The second hypothesis (H_2) can be accepted, namely that the use of accounting information systems has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur. The greater the effect of the use of accounting information systems, the higher the students' decision to pursue entrepreneurship.

Research conducted by Pramiswari and Dharmadiaksa (2017) states that the use of accounting information systems has a positive effect on decision-making in entrepreneurship. Research conducted by Sihombing (2021) states that the use of accounting information systems can affect entrepreneurial decision-making for 2016 Bachelor of Accounting students at Singaperbangsa University, Karawang. The results of the study show that the development of accounting information systems can influence the interest of the younger generation, especially students, in entrepreneurship. The higher the use of accounting information systems, the higher a person's decision-making capacity for entrepreneurship.

According to Lubis (2017), contingency theory is an approach that studies how contingent factors such as technology, culture, and the external environment can affect organizational behavior, design, and function. One of the factors that affect a person's decision-making in entrepreneurship is e-commerce, where the system is already digital-based and entrepreneurs can market their products without face-to-face meetings with customers, which will facilitate business activities and make people interested in entrepreneurship.

4.3. The Effect of Financial Knowledge on the Decision to Become an Entrepreneur

The third hypothesis (H_3) states that financial knowledge has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur. The results of the analysis in Table 7 show that the positive coefficient value is 5.896 with a significance level of 0.000, which is smaller than the real level in this study, namely $\alpha = 0.05$. This shows that financial knowledge has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur. The third hypothesis (H_3) can be accepted, namely that financial knowledge has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur, where the greater the effect of financial knowledge, the higher the students' decision to pursue entrepreneurship.

Contingency theory is an approach that studies how contingent factors such as technology, culture, and the external environment can affect organizational behavior, design, and function (Lubis, 2017). One of the factors that affects one's decision-making in entrepreneurship is financial knowledge. Someone who has an interest in entrepreneurship must understand how to manage company finances in order to generate the desired profit. Entrepreneurs who have financial knowledge will be able to prepare and know what the financial condition of their business is. Mature knowledge from the financial side will attract someone to make the decision to become an entrepreneur because it can predict the finances of his business so that the profit generated will be in accordance with the desired target.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

E-commerce has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur. The positive coefficient value is 5.285 with a significance level of 0.000, which is smaller than the real level in this study, namely $\alpha = 0.05$. This shows that e-commerce has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur. The first hypothesis (H_1) can be accepted, namely that e-commerce has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur, where the greater the effect of e-commerce, the higher the students' decision to pursue entrepreneurship. The use of accounting information systems has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur. The positive coefficient value is 4.533 with a significance level of 0.000, which is smaller than the real level in this study, namely $\alpha = 0.05$. This shows that the use of accounting information systems has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur. The second hypothesis (H_2) can be accepted, namely that the use of accounting information systems has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur. The greater the effect of the use of accounting information systems, the higher the students' decision to pursue entrepreneurship. Financial knowledge has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur. The positive coefficient value is 5.896 with a significance level of 0.000, which is smaller than the real level in this study, namely $\alpha = 0.05$. This shows that financial knowledge has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur. The third hypothesis (H_3) can be accepted, namely that financial knowledge has a positive effect on the decision to become an entrepreneur, where the greater the effect of financial knowledge, the higher the students' decision to pursue entrepreneurship. Based on the research conducted, some suggestions as the basis for thoughts and considerations for taking corrective actions and increasing further research are: (1) Students are expected to be interested and have motivation in entrepreneurship so that they have business ideas and run their business to the fullest. (2) Future researchers are expected to be able to conduct research on students at other universities or research objects other than students, according to the conditions encountered when conducting research.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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